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Nod2 functions in control of tropical disease likely occurring with pathogen specificity through NOD2-DDX helicase interactions.

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We describe here a general function for the human NACHT-domain containing nucleotide binding oligomerization domain NLR sensor *NOD2* in control of disease that occurs through infection with a tropical pathogen or pathogenic contact with an insect vector (transmission).

Results

1. Nod2 transcriptional program encompasses gene expression profiles of cells following infection with a variety of pathogens.

a. We detected through systems biologic methods a likely dominant role for NOD2 in perception or defense of infection by a pathogen.

b. The pathogens whose activity was enriched in the NOD2 transcription program, in human cells and tissues, included:

- i. Leishmania,
- ii. Amoebiasis resulting from *Entamoeba histolytica* infection,
- iii. Chagas Disease (American trypanosomiasis), and
- iv. African trypanosomiasis

2. We hypothesized NOD2 exerted influence on defense against infections from tropical diseases in a pathogen-specific manner. We previously described Nod2 control of DDX39A.

a. Separate investigators concurrently described a function for DDX39A in tropical disease defense, discovered through a genomic screening approach. DDX39A recognized a specific nucleic acid structure in the genome of the RNA virus Chikungunya.

3. To identify DDX helicases controlled by NOD2, we measured total transcription in a reporter system wherein HEK293 cells, which lack significant endogenous NOD2 expression, were engineered to stably express wild-type human NOD2. We previously described all or a majority of the findings obtained in the HEK293 reporter system. Helicases whose expression was controlled by NOD2, and whose expression was a major component of the NOD2 transcriptional program included:

- a. Ddx27,
- b. Ddx10,
- c. Ddx3x,
- d. Ddx18,
- e. Ddx52, and
- f. Ddx39a.

4. DDX27 was similarly expressed in primary human monocytes and in primary human monocytes from humans with endogenous Crohn's Disease containing mutations in NOD2.

5. Consistent with findings in primary monocytes, reporter cells expressing mutant NOD2 under stable expression expressed similar amounts of DDX27, with significant induction transcriptome-wide.

6. NOD2 expression is enriched and most abundant in monocyte and macrophage cells, and differentiation-dependent (highest in the macrophage).

7. DDX27 was modestly MDP inducible in monocytes.

8. MDP inducibility of DDX27 was similarly modest in monocytes from humans with CD containing mutation in NOD2, but slightly impaired when compared to monocytes from control individuals expressing endogenous wild-type NOD2.

- a. GSE69446

1 9. Ddx27 was expressed at equivalent (relatively abundant) quantities between monocyte and
2 macrophage.

3 a. GSE179636

4 10. We next measured total transcription in the human colon following one or sixty (60) days of
5 infection with *Entamoeba histolytica*.

6 a. GSE23750

7 11. Ddx27 helicase was activated (modestly but significantly) following infection with *Entamoeba*
8 *histolytica*.

9 12. We also studied total transcription following infection with *Trypanosoma cruzi*, which results in
10 Chagas Disease. IPS-derived cardiomyocytes were used for infection.

11 a. GSE129676

12 13. We again observed induction of a NOD2-regulated DDX helicase, DDX27, in cells following
13 infection with a tropical disease pathogen, *Trypanosoma cruzi*, at 24 hours.

14 14. We prefuntorily assessed NOD2-independent DDX27 pathogen defense interaction partners
15 through systems biologic transcriptome co-regulation approach: these genes provide immune support
16 during infection, but they are not NOD2 targets or interaction partners and instead are recruited based on
17 induction of and interaction with DDX27.

18 15. Chromatin modifying enzymes functioning in chromatin remodeling and erasure or deposition of
19 epigenetic marks were top DDX27 interactants, including subunits of the polycomb repressive complex
20 PRC2.

- 21 a. Mbd4
- 22 b. Cbx3
- 23 c. EED
- 24 d. Chd1
- 25 e. Suz12

26 16. Nuclear transport of RNA and protein cargoes was also a major target of DDX27 control or
27 expression. These genes included import and export receptors as well as nucleoporins that comprise the
28 nuclear pore complex :

- a. Kpnb1
- b. Xpo1
- c. Thoc1 and Thoc2
- d. Rae1
- e. Nup107
- f. Nup85
- g. Nup35

17. Ddx27 also controlled RNA binding protein expression

- a. Rbm27
- b. Rbm6
- c. Rbm12
- d. Rbm15

1 18. A fourth pathway of DDX27 control included other DDX helicases, suggesting DDX27 cooperates
2 in certain contexts with other DDX helicases.

- 3 a. Ddx55
- 4 b. Ddx23
- 5 c. Ddx18
- 6 d. Ddx47

7 19. Finally, we observed DDX27 control of translation machinery, consistent with a role for
8 translational control in host-pathogen dynamics.

- 9 a. Eif3M
- 10 b. Eif1AD

11 20. We described here a mechanism by which the innate immune receptor NOD2 exerts control of
12 infections resulting from tropical disease agents, in a pathogen-specific manner, through selective
13 induction of DDX helicases. DDX helicase interaction with nucleic acid structure in the pathogen genome
14 has previously been described by others. We present an alternative mechanism for specific pathogen
15 genome binding by a DDX following infection with a tropical disease agent through interactions with RBM
16 family molecules, which we found through unbiased transcriptomic identification of DDX27 interactants.

17 21. We suggest that separate from recruitment of the pathogen genome by the DDX helicase, that
18 each DDX helicase is likely to influence pathogen control through helicase-specific regulation of pathways
19 that enhanced immune control of tropical disease. For DDX27, these pathways included nuclear transport,
20 epigenetic modifications and chromatin remodeling, interactions with other DDX helicases, and
21 interactions with RNA-binding proteins. RBM-DDX interactions may confer, and function in, specific
22 DDX-pathogen genome interactions occurring through DDX27 but independent of direct DDX27
23 interactions.

24 22. We described here NOD2 control of tropical disease including diarrheal diseases transmitted
25 through fecal-oral route and bloodborne tropical diseases spread through insect vectors. This occurred
26 through selective activation of DDX helicases by NOD2, including DDX27.

27 23. NOD2-DDX induction functions through at least two mechanisms to exert pathogen control: by
28 binding of the pathogen for innate 'presentation' (pathogen sensing that is pathogen-specific but innate
immune-based), and by enhancing infection control through modulation of the host cell, like nuclear
transport (KPNB1 and XPO1) and translation (EIF1AD), and through control of nuclear transactivation
through epigenetic regulation involving PRC2 (EED and SUZ12) and methyl-binding and
chromodomain-containing molecules including MBD4 and CBX3.